

Assessment of Human Activity Pressures on Coastal Ecosystems of Pangandaran Beach, Indonesia

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Abstract

Pangandaran is a sub-district of Pangandaran Regency that includes a seaside area. Because most human activities take place in coastal areas, they have the potential to be heavily polluted. Human activities in the coastal sections of Pangandaran District are dominated by fishermen, tourists, fishing, and other activities that rely on coastal and marine resources to maintain the community's economy. The investigation was carried out in the Pangandaran Beach region of Pangandaran District, Pangandaran Regency. The goal of this research is to identify human activities and the pressure they put on coastal conditions, estimate the risk impact of human activities on ecosystems, and make decisions in order to prevent a rise in the chain of impacts. The study will be conducted in June 2023. This research focuses on the activities of fishing and tourism. The research method employed an ecosystem-based management strategy. The findings of this study indicate that there are seven pressures that have the ability to alter coastal conditions. Marine debris, which has an average IR value of 0.50, is an extremely dangerous pressure that causes acute damage to the ecosystem. The IR value of marine trash from tourism activities is 0.08 in the sublittoral sediment ecological component, whereas fishing operations have an IR value of 0.23. The resulting total IR (Impact Risk) value indicates that fishing activities are more valuable than tourism activities, with total values of 14.63 and 12.45, respectively. Fishing activities take place every day, putting more pressure on the environment, whereas tourism activities are seasonal. Pressure on the ecology is caused by marine debris, which has an average IR value of 0.50. The IR value of marine trash from tourism activities is 0.08 in the sublittoral sediment ecological component, whereas fishing operations have an IR value of 0.23.

Keywords: Coastal Conditions, Pangandaran Beach, Human Activities.

Introduction

Coastal areas serve as transition zones between land and sea ecosystems, and they are influenced by changes on both sides. Coastal areas have three characteristics: first, they are locations where various parts of land, water, and air interact, resulting from a dynamic balance of destruction and development of these three elements. Second, coastal areas serve as buffer zones and habitats for a diverse range of biological resources. Third, because coastal areas are rich in organic matter, they are fertile (Michel, 2010). Coastal areas have profitable natural resources that can be developed, such as mangrove, seagrass, and coral reef habitats. Pangandaran District is one of Pangandaran Regency's coastal sections, with a variety of tourist attractions including natural tourism, cultural tourism, artificial tourism, and traditional Pangandaran cuisine. Because most human

activities take place in coastal areas, they are vulnerable to substantial pollution consequences (Rizal et al., 2021). Human activities in the coastal sections of Pangandaran District are dominated by fishermen, tourists, fishing, and other activities that rely on coastal and marine resources to maintain the community's economy.

The use of coastal and marine resources is currently far from optimal and sustainable levels. Coastal areas that continue to lack supervision and care will cause damage or pollution to the environment. Damage to coastal and marine resource ecosystems in Indonesia is primarily caused by a lack of public knowledge. Oil pollution, waste, coastal erosion, mangrove destruction, tourism, and other factors all contribute to environmental degradation in coastal areas. The majority of this damage is caused by human activity in coastal areas (Valtria, 2010). The goal of this study is to examine the pressures of human activities that pose a risk to the ecosystem. To accomplish this, we identify human activities and the pressures they place on coastal conditions, link them to assessments of environmental impacts, and indicate the severity of ecosystem pressures that affect coastal conditions. This study employs an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach that takes into account the entire ecosystem, including humans.

Material and Method

This investigation was carried out along the coast of Pangandaran Beach in Pangandaran Regency (Figure 1). Pangandaran District is a national tourist attraction (ODTW) with a protected nature reserve. The majority of Pangandaran District's residents work in agriculture, namely rice farming, secondary crops, and fishing. As much as 1.99% of the total population in Pangandaran District is employed as fishermen. Aside from that, the population's other professions include trading and labor. The initial poll will be conducted between the end of August and November 2024, with the research continuing until June 2025.

Figure 1. Pangandaran Regency is located in West Java.

The data in this study is based on the findings of purposive sample interviews with specified sources in order to get suggestions from major sources regarding environmental actions. The data was then supplemented with secondary data gathered from local agencies, including the Pangandaran Regency Marine, Fisheries, and Food Security Service and the Pangandaran Regency Tourism and Culture Service, as well as direct field observations. Statistics on community activities in the coastal environment were gathered through literature searches in journals and books, as well as interviews with local communities and associated sources for supporting statistics and general information. Aside from that, secondary data from the local government is utilized, particularly from the Pangandaran Regency Marine, Fisheries, and Food Security Service. Following the identification of numerous sectors as starting hypotheses, the following stage is to define the sort of pressure that causes hazards in each of the identified ecological components.

Results and Discussion

The Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) Framework. The DPSIR framework is utilized to gather information from the literature on the primary issue of marine waste in the Pangandaran sub-district, particularly the Pangandaran coast. This approach for analyzing and managing environmental risks based on a single chain of cause-effect interactions is widely employed (Troian et al., 2021; GRID Arendal, 2005). In this approach, human activities are driven by socioeconomic and sociocultural factors, which can either raise or decrease environmental pressure. Human activities on the environment effect pressure, with states that reflect environmental circumstances and can have an impact on the ecosystem, resulting in a reaction as an appraisal of actions in terms of management techniques (Pirrone et al., 2005).

Driver

The problem of rubbish and waste in this region is not immune to the effects of economic growth, namely the expansion of tourism and fishing operations, which can attract more tourists and inhabitants at times. According to the Pangandaran Tourism and Culture Department (Disparbud), the number of tourists has fluctuated over the last five years, but the tourism sector and tourism will continue to grow. If not adequately controlled, this has the potential to exacerbate existing pressure levels. Aside from that, the high level of fishing activity and the traffic of wooden fishing machine boats were discovered to be the activities causing the most pressure. This location has promise in the tourism and fishing industries, which can boost the economy and impact pressure levels.

Pressure

The pressure generated by these forces has the potential to have an impact on the coastal ecosystem. According to this research, marine debris found in coastal or terrestrial environmental zones, as well as marine settings, exerts the most pressure. Rubbish in this area comes from tourist attractions, fishermen's fishing gear, dwellings or homestays, and the water. The volume of maritime debris and rubbish will increase during the Christmas season. The behavior of tourists and local communities, which still reflects limited knowledge of environmental protection, is one of the factors contributing to increased littering behavior. This is consistent with Boelee's dkk. (2019), which explains that human performance is influenced by changing social and economic conditions, as well as the presence of various technologies in the environment.

State

Pangandaran District has nine garbage disposal sites, each with a capacity of 48 m³. Every day, cleaning staff take up trash in this region. This does not preclude the idea of an evenly cleaned environment. Public knowledge and tourists who still do not care about the environment have resulted in garbage scattered along major access routes, particularly in retail malls. Fishermen in this area continue to disregard the environment, dumping fishing gear garbage on the coast. The shopping center's state, which includes scattered debris and spilled water from selling fish, makes the area around the sales appear dusty and shabby. A contaminated environment endangers human health, reduces aesthetic value, causes economic losses, and disrupts natural ecosystems.

Impact

When environmental conditions deteriorate, it has an impact on the surrounding ecosystem, resulting in the emergence of situations that are harmful to humans. The accumulation of garbage and poor management in coastal areas might have a negative influence on health. Piles of garbage and filthy settings promote the growth of bacteria that are harmful to humans. Environmental contamination caused by garbage and rubbish damages components in the ecosystem.

Response

Finally, the responder has control over the reaction to all drivers, pressures, states, and affects. The local government has taken steps to solve this issue, including education and garbage processing training. (Apriliani et al., 2021) also conducted socialization with beach visitors, and based on the findings of his research, he concluded that socialization in the form of lectures/discussions and beach clean-up actions can be used to ensure that the target audience understands the importance of protecting the coastal and marine environment. Rizal et al. (2021) used outreach to raise public awareness and address the impact of garbage on the coastal ecosystem. The findings of this study indicate an increase in public knowledge of the coastal environment.

Conclusions

This study has successfully identified human activities that exert strain on coastal environments. These activities include tourism and fishing. These two activities yielded seven physical pressures that could endanger the environment: marine debris, sediment changes, smothering, selective extraction of species, the introduction of organic materials, barriers to species movement, and the introduction of non-synthetic compounds. The impact chain assessment generates pressure from marine debris with a low IR value, which is thought to have a severe influence on the ecosystem. The IR value of marine waste from tourism and fishing activities is 0.08 and 0.23 for the sublittoral sediment ecological component, which has an influence on species such as seagrass and has high risk criteria. Fishing is regarded as the most dangerous activity. The method that needs to be adopted to mitigate environmental risks caused by human activities in this area is to raise fishermen's environmental awareness in Pangandaran District and improve adaptive ecosystem management. As a result, additional research is needed to examine concerns in other sectors of the Pangandaran District in order to determine the environmental dangers in this region.

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